

DRILL-Q: Delay-Responsive Intelligent Learning for Latency-sensitive QoS

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Abstract—Resource scheduling plays a critical role in managing congestion in modern networks. This problem is inherently complex, as it requires timely decision-making where previous allocations influence future resource availability. Traditional scheduling policies aim to guarantee Quality of Service (QoS) while ensuring fair resource distribution. More recently, Machine Learning (ML)-based schedulers have been proposed to enhance scheduling efficiency. However, existing solutions fail to explicitly integrate Guaranteed Flow Bit Rate (Guaranteed Flow Bit Rate (GFBR)) constraints into Reinforcement Learning (RL)-based scheduling decisions. In this paper, we propose DRILL-Q, a novel RL-based QoS-aware MAC scheduler designed to manage multi-flow traffic while explicitly ensuring GFBR compliance. DRILL-Q leverages a reward function that incorporates packet delay budget (Packet Delay Budget (PDB)), head-of-line (Head-of-Line (HOL)) delay, and priority levels to optimize scheduling decisions. Simulation results demonstrate that DRILL-Q successfully prioritizes traffic based on its QoS requirements, while significantly enhancing fairness among flows with the same 5G QoS Identifier (5QI). Compared to traditional and deterministic scheduling algorithms, DRILL-Q achieves superior resource allocation, reducing delay and jitter while maintaining higher throughput under congested network conditions.

Index Terms—QoS Scheduling, RL, MAC Scheduler, GFBR, Multi-Flow Traffic Management, Network Resource Allocation

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in 5G and beyond networks have enabled the support of a wide range of real-time applications, each with distinct Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. From industrial automation to remote surgery and autonomous vehicles to eXtended Reality (XR), all these emerging applications require stringent latencies and high reliability to ensure seamless operation. Such latency-sensitive applications require more advanced scheduling mechanisms, including proper traffic flow treatment, to allow seamless real-time operation. In addition, applications such as the XR, can generate multi-flow traffic, introducing additional complexity to the scheduling process. To address these challenges, 5G New Radio (NR) introduced the QoS model that enhances traffic management by shifting the QoS control to a finer granularity level, known as the QoS flow. Additionally, it introduces a two-level mapping of IP-packets of Service Data Flows (SDFs) to appropriate QoS flows handled by the 5G Core (5GC), and QoS Flows to Data Radio Bearers (DRBs) managed by the Radio Access Network (RAN) [1]. Such decoupling of the functionality

between the 5GC and the RAN, allows for more flexible QoS management of the network traffic. Moreover, it extends the LTE QoS classification model, and apart from Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR) and non-GBR, it also supports Delay-critical GBR (DC-GBR) flows. As such, the 5G QoS model establishes a framework for latency-sensitive multi-flow traffic management, enabling differentiation based on specific QoS needs.

While 3GPP specifies the framework of the 5G QoS model, it does not provide specific guidelines for implementing MAC scheduling algorithms, leaving room for further research and innovation [2]. Our previous work [3], [4] introduced a novel QoS MAC scheduler that prioritizes DC-GBR traffic, enhancing delay and throughput. However, despite these improvements, further optimization is necessary to prevent penalizing other traffic types, which could lead to user starvation. Meanwhile, Reinforcement Learning (RL) is increasingly being employed to enhance 5G scheduling due to its focus on real-time decision-making and dynamic adaptability—both critical for meeting QoS requirements [2].

However, most RL-based schedulers in previous studies follow one of three main approaches. Some classify traffic broadly into ultra-reliable, low-latency communication (URLLC), Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), or other service types, without considering the individual QoS Flow-level requirements [5]–[7]. Others focus on prioritizing delay-sensitive traffic but do not comprehensively account for all 5QI attributes such as Packet Delay Budget (PDB), Priority Level, and Guaranteed Flow Bit Rate (GFBR) together [8], [9]. Another common approach is to optimize scheduling based solely on GFBR while overlooking other critical 5QI attributes, such as PDB and Priority Level, and without explicitly addressing Multi-flow UE scenarios, such as [10], [11]. Additionally, these works that do consider 5QI characteristics still fail to incorporate the complexities introduced by multi-flow traffic.

In this paper, we propose Delay-Responsive Intelligent Learning for Latency-sensitive QoS (DRILL-Q), a novel RL-based QoS MAC scheduler that builds upon our previous work [3], [4] to enhance traffic prioritization and user fairness in multi-flow scenarios. Using the Deep Double Q-Learning (DDQN) algorithm, DRILL-Q dynamically allocates resources based on each flow’s 5QI requirements, including PDB, Priority Level, and GFBR. Unlike traditional ap-

proaches that minimize latency or maximize throughput at the service level, DRILL-Q ensures packets are transmitted within each flow’s PDB, effectively meeting per-flow QoS constraints. We adopt DDQN for its stability and effectiveness in dynamic scheduling, utilizing a value-based approach to ensure reliable action selection while optimizing QoS-based resource allocation. DRILL-Q is implemented in the ns-3 5G-LENA simulator [12], extended with ns3-gym [13] for AI/ML support. This integration enables dynamic testing and open-source development of RL-based schedulers in a simulated 5G environment¹.

Our main contributions are summarized as follows:

- To the best of our knowledge, unlike existing approaches, our work is the first to explicitly integrate 5QI requirements at the QoS Flow level using RL.
- We propose a generalized scheduler designed to handle all traffic types, while providing enhanced performance for multi-flow traffic by explicitly accounting for its unique characteristics.
- Utilization of DDQN-based RL to dynamically allocate resources based on each flow’s QoS requirements (PDB, Priority Level, GFBR, etc.)
- ns-3-based simulations demonstrating improved fairness and performance compared to existing GFBR-aware schedulers.

II. RELATED WORK

The studies in [5]–[9] apply RL for 5G resource allocation to meet the QoS requirements of various services, addressing the coexistence of low-latency and high-throughput traffic. The main challenge in these studies is ensuring the latency and reliability requirements of services such as URLLC while simultaneously considering other types of traffic. The authors in [8] proposed a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based resource allocation method for environments where low-latency and non-low-latency traffic coexist, employing a negative reward mechanism for increased latency in low-latency traffic. Similarly, M. Elsayed et al. introduced an RL-based scheduling method [6], which dynamically adapts resource allocation and transmission power to satisfy the latency and reliability requirements of URLLC. Furthermore, the works in [5], [7], [9] explore a broader range of services by integrating network slicing with RL, enabling service-specific resource allocation through learning slice-defined parameters.

However, the models in these studies rely on experimental and predictive values obtained through computationally complex simulations, without explicitly incorporating QoS requirements defined by 5G QoS Identifier (5QI) values, such as PDB and guaranteed bit rate. These parameters are essential for ensuring the QoS of 5G DC-GBR resources. Several studies have investigated the GFBR requirements of 5G GBR and DC-GBR resources. For instance, the authors in [11] propose an optimization strategy for resource allocation between GBR and non-GBR flows, ensuring that GBR flows receive their GFBR, while allocating the remaining resources to non-GBR flows

¹The basic framework is publicly available in the official 5G-LENA GitLab (release v3.4): <https://gitlab.com/cttc-lena/nr>

based on 5QI values. The study in [14] further prioritizes GBR flow allocation while maintaining fairness through Channel Quality Information (CQI)-based channel-aware scheduling strategies. Additionally, [10] presents a channel-aware scheduling approach that integrates CQI and numerology while considering GFBR. Despite addressing GBR traffic, these studies do not account for the complexities of multi-flow traffic scenarios. Moreover, none of these studies explicitly incorporate 5QI-defined QoS parameters, making them impractical for real-world 5G deployments.

Our previous work [3], [4] also considered the GFBR requirements of GBR and DC-GBR flows. Additionally, by introducing the QoS LC Assignment algorithm, it proposed a resource distribution strategy among logical channels of multi-flow installed UEs. However, the algorithm assigned disproportionately high weights to UEs with DC-GBR flows, leading to resource starvation for UEs without such flows. The study in [15] extended our previous work using Lyapunov optimization, focusing on enhancing resource utilization efficiency.

According to 3GPP TS 23.501 [16], GBR and DC-GBR flows are authorized on an “on-demand” basis, meaning their priority in resource allocation is dynamic and adaptive. This is particularly relevant due to the Flow Bit Rate requirements of these flows, especially GFBR. To address these limitations, we propose an RL-based scheduler that adaptively allocates resources to ensure at least GFBR compliance even in multi-flow scenarios. Our proposed scheduler, DRILL-Q, allocates resources based on Head-of-Line (HOL) delay and priority while considering the GFBR of GBR and DC-GBR flows, integrating the QoS LC Assignment algorithm from [3].

III. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a system where a gNB is associated with U UEs, represented by the set \mathcal{U} , managing N flows denoted as \mathcal{N} , distributed across these UEs. Each flow is linked to a specific UE, and for each $u \in \mathcal{U}$, the set of its flows is \mathcal{N}_u . These definitions lay the groundwork for the RL problem, where state, action, and reward components are formulated to optimize scheduling decisions in the RL framework.

A. System Overview

In our system, the Next Generation Node Base (gNB) assigns resource granularity to a User Equipments (UEs) based on the selected action of the DDQN model. The resource granularity is determined by the Multiple Access Scheme adopted in the system, such as Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) and Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA), which influence how resources are allocated across users and time slots. After performing resource allocations within a single slot, the scheduler distributes the assigned bytes of each UEs to its associated flows using the QoS LC Assignment algorithm [3]. The algorithm prioritizes resource allocation for GBR and DC-GBR flows to satisfy their guaranteed bit rate requirements. Any remaining bytes, determined based on GFBR, are then distributed among non-GBR flows in a Round Robin (RR) fashion. If the total required bytes for GBR and DC-GBR flows exceed the assigned bytes,

the scheduler distributes the available resources among them in a RR fashion. Otherwise, it fully satisfies their demands before allocating any remaining resources to non-GBR flows. A detailed description of the algorithm is available in [3].

In our system, the scheduler operates at the granularity of resource units. As illustrated in Fig. 1, our proposed DDQN module selects an action $a_{i,t}$ for each resource unit i within time slot t , given the current state $S_{i,t}$. Each action corresponds to assigning the resource unit to a UE, and a reward $R_{i,t}$ is computed based on the outcome of that assignment. Once all resource units within slot t have been allocated to UEs based on the actions selected by the DDQN module, the system aggregates the assigned bytes for each UE u over the slot, denoted as $B_{u,t}$. The QoS LC Assignment algorithm then distributes these bytes among the UE's associated flows, resulting in a flow-level allocation $B_{u,t}^{LC}$. Further details on the DDQN module are provided in the following section.

Fig. 1: The block diagram for entire system

B. RL Problem Formulation

1) *State*: The two-dimensional matrix of size $(U, 4)$ is used to represent the state space, where U is the total number of UEs and 4 is the size of the state vector. Each row represents the state of UE u for resource unit i at time slot t . To construct the current state $S_{i,t}$, the system selects a representative flow using logic similar to the QoS LC Assignment algorithm. For each UE, it selects the representative flow following Algorithm 1. As an initial step, the scheduler constructs the set of **active** flows \mathcal{N}_u^A for each UE u , which consists of flows with packets awaiting transmission in their queues. Then, it sorts the active GBR and DC-GBR flows, $\mathcal{N}_{\text{GBR} \cup \text{DC-GBR}, u}^A$, in ascending order of Priority Level, where a lower value indicates a higher priority. In the system, the Priority Level follows the default values defined by standardized 5QI [16].

Then, the scheduler iterates through the sorted list, accumulating the required bytes of each flow and comparing them with the cumulative assigned bytes $B_{u,t}$, which represents the total number of bytes assigned to UE u from the 1st to the i -th resource unit in slot t . The required bytes of each flow correspond to the ratio of GFBP for the slot duration. If the accumulated required bytes $B_{\text{sum}}^{\text{req}}$ exceed the current assigned bytes $B_{u,t}$, the corresponding GBR or DC-GBR flow is selected as the representative flow for UE u . Otherwise, the

non-GBR flow with the highest value of $\frac{HOL_n}{PDB_n \times P_n}$ is chosen as the representative flow.

After selecting the representative flow for each UE, the scheduler constructs the state matrix. Each vector comprises three essential features: the priority level of the representative flow P_{u,n^*} , the current HOL delay of the representative flow HOL_{u,n^*} , which indicates the time that flow n in the queue has been waiting, and the current average throughput $\bar{\Lambda}_{u,t}$. The current average throughput is calculated using Exponential Moving Average (EMA), as shown in Eq. (1):

$$\bar{\Lambda}_{u,t} = (1 - \alpha) \times \bar{\Lambda}_{u,t-1} + \alpha \times \Lambda_{u,t} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\Lambda}_{u,t-1}$ represents the average throughput of UE u until the previous time slot $t-1$, α represents the smoothing factor, and $\Lambda_{u,t}$ represents the instantaneous throughput of UE u during the time slot t until the i -th resource unit, which is calculated using the assigned bytes $B_{u,t}$, following as:

$$\Lambda_{u,t} = \frac{B_{u,t} \cdot 8}{2^{-\mu} \cdot 10^{-3}} \quad (2)$$

Then, the state for UE u is represented as:

$$S_{u,i,t} = (P_{u,n^*}, HOL_{u,n^*}, \bar{\Lambda}_{u,i,t}) \quad (3)$$

and the state $S_{i,t}$ is represented as:

$$S_{i,t} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{1,i,t} \\ S_{2,i,t} \\ \vdots \\ S_{U,i,t} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where each row in the state matrix is ordered according to the RNTI of the corresponding UE, ensuring consistency between state representation and action selection.

2) *Action*: The action space consists of U possible actions, where each action corresponds to assigning the resource unit to one of the U UEs in the system. The selected action $a_{i,t}$ represents the RNTI of the UE when the state $S_{i,t}$ is given. For each state, the DDQN module selects a UE to assign the current resource unit i during time slot t based on the estimated Q-values, which incorporate both immediate rewards and long-term expected returns for selecting each UE.

Once the action is selected, the corresponding UE's cumulative assigned bytes $B_{u,t}$ are incremented by the size of the i -th resource unit. These updates are accumulated throughout the slot t , and at the end of the slot, the final $B_{u,t}$ values are used as input to the QoS LC Assignment algorithm, which distributes the assigned bytes among each UE's active flows.

3) *Reward*: The proposed reward function is designed to meet the PDB requirement while considering the priority level of the flows. To quantify the urgency of scheduling decisions, the system computes a scheduling urgency metric for each flow n based on its HOL delay, PDB, and priority level as follows:

$$\Phi_n = \frac{HOL_n}{PDB_n} \times \frac{100}{P_n} \quad (5)$$

This metric increases as the HOL delay grows or as the PDB and priority level decrease, ensuring that more urgent flows receive higher scheduling priority. The scalar 100 is

Algorithm 1 Representative Flow Selection for UE u

- 1: **Input:** The Flow Set of UE u \mathcal{N}_u , numerology μ , resource unit i , time slot t
 - 2: **Output:** Select representative flow $n^* \in \mathcal{N}_u$
 - 3: Initialize $B_{\text{sum}}^{\text{gur}} \leftarrow 0$
 - 4: Sort $\mathcal{N}_{\text{GBR} \cup \text{DC-GBR}, u}^A$ in ascending order of Priority Level
 - 5: **for** each $n \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{GBR} \cup \text{DC-GBR}, u}^A$ **do**
 - 6: $B_{\text{sum}}^{\text{gur}} \leftarrow B_{\text{sum}}^{\text{gur}} + \left(\frac{\text{GFBR}_n}{8} \cdot 2^{-\mu} \cdot 10^{-3} \right)$
 - 7: **if** $B_{\text{sum}}^{\text{gur}} > B_{u,t}$ **then**
 - 8: **return** n
 - 9: **end if**
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Sort $\mathcal{N}_{\text{non-GBR}, u}^A$ in descending order of $\frac{\text{HOL}_n}{\text{PDB}_n \times P_n}$
 - 12: **return** the first element of $\mathcal{N}_{\text{non-GBR}, u}^A$
-

introduced to amplify the impact of the priority level, thereby enhancing the numerical difference in urgency among flows with different QoS requirements. This allows the scheduler to better distinguish high-priority flows, especially when the values of HOL_n and PDB_n are close.

Then, the urgency of each UE is obtained as:

$$\Phi_u = \frac{K \cdot N_u}{\Lambda_{u,t} + \zeta} \times \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}_u} \Phi_n \quad (6)$$

To reflect the multi-flow characteristics of UEs, the urgency of a UE is computed as the sum of the urgency values of all its active flows. Additionally, to implicitly incorporate fairness between UEs, we divide the sum of urgency of \mathcal{N}_u by the average throughput per flow. It is calculated as $\frac{\Lambda_{u,t} + \zeta}{N_u}$ where ζ is a very small constant to prevent 0. K is a constant to prevent the reward from becoming too small, as multiple division operations are involved in the reward calculation, as shown in Eq. (5) and Eq. (6).

The total system reward is calculated based on the urgency values of UEs. The system reward $R_{i,t}$ for action $a_{i,t}$ given state $S_{i,t}$ is defined as the difference between the urgency of the selected UE u^* and the average urgency of the remaining UEs:

$$R_{i,t} = \Phi_{u^*} - \frac{1}{U-1} \times \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus \{u^*\}} \Phi_u \quad (7)$$

To prevent excessively large values, which may negatively impact the training process, we use the normalized reward $\hat{R}_{i,t}$ during training:

$$\hat{R}_{i,t} = \text{sgn}(R_{i,t}) \cdot \log(1 + R_{i,t}) \quad (8)$$

where $\text{sgn}(\cdot)$ denotes the sign function, which returns +1 if the input is positive, -1 if negative, and 0 otherwise. This normalization ensures that the reward values remain within a manageable range, improving the stability of the learning process.

C. DDQN Module

In the system, we use DDQN for scheduling decisions, which is one of the value-based RL algorithms. While policy-based reinforcement learning methods such as Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), Advantage Actor-Critic (A2C), and Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) have demonstrated strong performance in various scheduling and control problems, their reliance on probability distributions or weight-based action selection mechanisms can degrade the accuracy of learning optimal UE selection, especially as the number of UEs increases.

To address this issue, we employ a value-based RL approach. Additionally, unlike traditional Deep Q-Learning (DQN), which suffers from Q-value overestimation due to the max operator in target updates, DDQN mitigates this issue by using a separate target Q-network. This approach stabilizes training and prevents the agent from being overly optimistic in its action selection.

In the DDQN module, the Q-network takes the state $S_{i,t}$ as input and outputs Q-values for all possible actions, representing the expected cumulative rewards for selecting each action. The network consists of three fully connected layers with ReLU activation functions, and the final layer outputs U Q-values corresponding to the U candidate UEs:

$$Q(S_{i,t}, a; \theta) = f_{\theta}(S_{i,t}), \quad (9)$$

where θ represents the neural network parameters.

The DDQN module is trained using experience replay with a replay buffer. At each step, the module stores a transition $(S_{i,t}, a_{i,t}, R_{i,t}, S_{i+1,t}, d)$, where d is the done signal indicating episode termination. A mini-batch of M transitions is sampled from the buffer for training. One episode ends when the resource allocation of all resource units in time slot t is completed, and training is performed periodically. The Q-value update follows the Double Q-learning framework. First, the next action is selected using the online Q-network:

$$a' = \arg \max_a Q_{\text{online}}(S_{i+1,t}, a; \theta). \quad (10)$$

Then, the target Q-value is computed using the target Q-network:

$$Q_{\text{target}} = \hat{R}_{i,t} + (1-d) \cdot \gamma \cdot Q_{\text{target}}(S_{i+1,t}, a'; \theta^-), \quad (11)$$

where $\hat{R}_{i,t}$ is the normalized reward as defined in Eq. (8), γ is the discount factor, θ represents the parameters of the online Q-network, and θ^- represents the parameters of the target Q-network.

To stabilize training, the target network parameters are updated using a soft update mechanism:

$$\theta^- \leftarrow \tau \cdot \theta + (1-\tau) \cdot \theta^-, \quad (12)$$

where τ is a small positive value controlling the update rate.

Additionally, to balance exploration and exploitation, the agent follows an ϵ -greedy policy. The exploration rate ϵ is initially set to 1.0 and gradually decays to a minimum threshold ϵ_{\min} over time:

$$\epsilon \leftarrow \max(\epsilon_{\min}, \epsilon \cdot \lambda), \quad (13)$$

where λ is the decay factor controlling the rate of exploration reduction.

IV. EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

As our evaluation framework, we use the ns-3 NR module (5G-LENA) simulator [17] and we extend it to support AI/ML through integration with the ns3-gym module [13]. 5G-LENA provides a realistic simulation environment for modeling 5G RAN components [18], while the ns3-gym enables interaction with RL algorithms through OpenAI Gym environments.

A. Module and Class Architecture

The proposed DRILL-Q scheduler is implemented in the 5G-LENA simulator with new classes for both TDMA and OFDMA access modes, named `NrMacSchedulerTdmaAi` and `NrMacSchedulerOfdmaAi`, respectively. These classes allocate resources to users by utilizing the actions passed from the DDQN model implemented in Python. These classes schedule UEs based on the action as described in Section III-B. The DDQN model is implemented according to Section III-C. To manage and store UE-specific information used in learning, we implemented an additional class named `NrMacSchedulerUeInfoAi`.

We extended the ns3-gym module with a new class named `NrMacSchedulerAiNs3GymEnv` that gathers information from the 5G-LENA classes and converts it into the format specified by the ns3-gym to train the DDQN model. Details of the data format used can be found in [13]. Data transmission is handled via an interface in ns3-gym called `OpenGymInterface` employing ZeroMQ [19], an asynchronous messaging library. The proposed architecture is shown in Fig. 2.

Notice that the implementation details of the classes are beyond the scope of this paper; therefore, we focus only on the high-level architecture.

Fig. 2: The module and class architecture at resource unit i in time slot t

B. Evaluation Scenario

For the evaluation of the proposed DRILL-Q scheduler, we implemented a simulation scenario configured with the parameters shown in Table I. We study a single-cell topology with varying numbers of UEs. Each UE is configured with either Application 1, 2, or 3. Application 1 consists of a single non-GBR flow ($5QI = 80$), while Application 2 consists

of two flows: one non-GBR flow ($5QI = 80$) and one DC-GBR flow ($5QI = 87$). Additionally, Application 3 consists of a single GBR flow ($5QI = 1$). For the DC-GBR flow, the `e_rabGuaranteedBitRate` is set to a fixed value, as shown in Table I. To create a saturated network condition for all flows, the Packet Size is set to 3000 bytes, and the Packet Generation Interval is set to 1 ms. These parameters are chosen to induce network congestion, which is necessary to evaluate the schedulers under high-load conditions.

The QoS characteristics of the flows used in the evaluation are shown in Table II, following the specifications in 3GPP TS 23.501 [16]. The Priority Level of each flow corresponds to the Default Priority Level defined in the standard.

To ensure realistic buffer management, we set the RLC Maximum Buffer Size to $10 \cdot 2^{10}$ bytes per UE. This limitation prevents excessive packet accumulation at the RLC layer, which could otherwise introduce excessive queuing delays and impact the fairness of scheduling decisions. Additionally, PDCP Discarding is enabled, allowing outdated packets to be discarded at the PDCP layer. This prevents unnecessary retransmissions and reduces HOL delay for UEs experiencing severe congestion.

For the evaluation of the DRILL-Q scheduler, we utilized RR, Proportional Fair (PF), and QoS-aware schedulers [4] as benchmarks. The LC assignment, which distributes scheduled resources of a user to its different logical channels, was configured to use the LC Assignment setting. The hyperparameters used for training the DDQN module are listed in Table III.

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters for the Evaluation Scenario

Scenario Parameter	Value
Carrier Frequency	4 GHz
Bandwidth	10 MHz
Numerology	1
Multiple Access Scheme	OFDMA
gNB/UE Transmit Power	gNB: 43 dBm / UE: 23 dBm
gNB/UE Antenna Height	gNB: 10m / UE: 1.5 m
Propagation Model	3GPP UMa TR 38.901
Shadowing	Disabled
Fading	Disabled
Channel Condition	LoS, No updates
<code>e_rabGuaranteedBitRate</code>	5 Mbps
Packet Size	3000 bytes
Packet Generation Interval	1 ms
ζ (Small Positive Constant)	10^{-6}
Memory Update Interval	2^{11} steps
RLC Maximum Buffer Size	$10 \cdot 2^{10}$
PDCP Discarding	Enabled

TABLE II: QoS Characteristics based on 5QI

5QI	Resource Type	Priority Level	PDB (ms)
1	GBR	20	100
80	non-GBR	68	10
87	DC-GBR	25	5

TABLE III: DDQN Hyperparameters

Parameter	Value
Hidden Layer Size	256
Learning Rate	0.001
Discount Factor (γ)	0.98
Target Update Rate (τ)	0.005
Initial Epsilon (ϵ_0)	1.0
Exploration Decay Factor (λ)	0.995
Replay Buffer Size	10,000
Batch Size	64

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed DRILL-Q scheduler across two scenarios with different UE and flow configurations. The first scenario, based on [4], serves as a baseline for identifying the key issues addressed by DRILL-Q. We assess throughput, delay, and jitter, representing the guaranteed bit rate for a GBR and DC-GBR flows as a red horizontal line.

A. Scenario 1: 2 UEs, 3 Flows (Mixed GBR and Non-GBR)

In Scenario 1, two UEs connect to the same gNB. One is configured with Application 1 and the other one with Application 2 (two flows). This setup tests a mixed flow configuration with different QoS needs, serving as a baseline for the DRILL-Q scheduler. We assess scheduler performance under light and heavy saturation, using 10 MHz bandwidth.

The simulation results are presented in Fig. 3. In this scenario, the baseline QoS scheduler presents high disparity in delay between the two UEs. Specifically, the non-GBR flow of UE 1 (Application 1) experiences three times higher delay compared to the non-GBR flow of UE 2 (Application 2), as shown in Fig. 3b. This arises from the way that the weights are calculated in the QoS scheduler, where the DC-GBR flow's weight is multiplied by a delay budget factor related to HOL delay and PDB, promoting prioritization of that type of flows, while the non-GBR flow of UE 2 benefits from this prioritization. Additionally, it can be observed that the jitter values for UE 1 non-GBR traffic are increased, indicating unstable access to the channel.

Moreover, RR and PF schedulers allocate resources uniformly, without considering the number of flows or the 5QI characteristics. Consequently, these schedulers achieve higher throughput and lower delay for UE 1, but fail to prioritize the DC-GBR flow (5QI 87). This indicates that both RR and PF schedulers lack a mechanism to address the unique requirements of mixed flow configurations effectively.

On the other hand, the DRILL-Q scheduler reduces delay and jitter for the non-GBR flow of UE 1 while prioritizing the DC-GBR flow, thereby achieving a more balanced allocation among UEs. As shown in Figs. 3a and 3b, DRILL-Q successfully satisfies both PDB and GFBR requirements, whereas the PDB requirement of UE 1 is not met in the QoS scheduler. In Fig. 3c, although the jitter of UE 1 appears relatively high in DRILL-Q, the overall jitter remains below 1 ms. Thus, DRILL-Q effectively allocates resources based on flow characteristics,

ensuring a more stable traffic pattern and achieving a better balance in terms of delay and throughput among UEs.

B. Scenario 2: 4 UEs, 6 Flows (Increased Load)

Scenario 2 extends the topology to four UEs, all connected to the same gNB. Two UEs are configured with Application 1 and the other two UEs with Application 2. This scenario allows us to assess the scheduler's performance in a more complex network environment, consisting of multiple UEs with multi-flow traffic, each with varying requirements. By increasing the number of UEs, we evaluate how the scheduler handles resource competition and prioritizes flows with different QoS constraints, ensuring fair and efficient allocation under increased network load.

The simulation results for Scenario 2 are shown in Fig. 4. In this setup, the QoS scheduler results in a high disparity in delay and jitter among the non-GBR flows across different UEs. For instance, UE 1 and UE 3, each configured with a single non-GBR flow (Application 1), experience significantly higher delays compared to UE 2 and UE 4, which have multiple flows (Application 2), as shown in Fig. 4b. In addition to increased delay, the throughput of UE 1 and UE 3 is almost zero. This prioritization occurs due to the weighting mechanism favoring DC-GBR traffic, leading to imbalanced resource allocation. Similarly, the jitter values for UE 1 and UE 3 non-GBR flows are significantly higher in the QoS scheduler, as shown in Fig. 4c, indicating intermittent channel access.

In contrast, we can observe that UEs with multiple-flow exhibit near-zero throughput in the RR and PF schedulers while providing higher throughput to the single-flow UEs at the expense of failing to meet the DC-GBR requirements, as shown in Fig. 4a. This anomaly stems not from the schedulers themselves but from the 5G-LENA implementation of RR, which lacks sufficient memory, leading to unfair resource allocation under limited resources.

On the other hand, our proposed DRILL-Q scheduler achieves a more balanced resource distribution among UEs, prioritizing DC-GBR flows while ensuring fair throughput allocation for single-flow non-GBR UEs. Moreover, DRILL-Q demonstrates stable delay across all flows, maintaining values below 10 ms, as shown in Fig. 4b, and stable jitter, as shown in Fig. 4c. These results highlight the ability of DRILL-Q to maintain QoS requirements while preventing excessive delay and jitter disparities among different traffic types.

C. Scenario 3: 4 UEs, 6 Flows (GBR Flow Adjustment)

Scenario 3 builds upon Scenario 2 while introducing a broader range of QoS flow types. In this scenario, one of the UEs previously assigned to Application 2 is now configured with Application 3, which consists of a single GBR flow. This modification allows us to analyze how the scheduler handles all three 5G QoS resource types: non-GBR, GBR, and DC-GBR. By incorporating a more diverse set of flow types, we evaluate whether the scheduler can maintain efficient and fair resource allocation while ensuring that GBR flows meet their GFBR requirements. Additionally, as this scenario includes three GBR flows, we adjust the GBR configuration by reducing

Fig. 3: Simulation Results of 2 UEs with 3 flows for 10 MHz bandwidth with OFDMA mode.

Fig. 4: Simulation Results of 4 UEs with 6 flows for 10 MHz bandwidth with OFDMA mode

`e_rabGuaranteedBitRate` from 5 Mbps to 2.5 Mbps to account for the increased resource demand.

The simulation results are shown in Fig. 5. As illustrated in Fig. 5a, only our proposed scheduler DRILL-Q is able to satisfy the GFBR requirements for both GBR and DC-GBR flows. In contrast, the throughput of the GBR flow under the QoS scheduler remains as low as that of non-GBR flows with single-flow configurations, despite its guaranteed bitrate requirement. This behavior can be attributed to the weight calculation mechanism in the QoS scheduler, which tends to favor DC-GBR flows due to their dual-constrained nature—having to meet both guaranteed throughput and strict delay requirements—making them more sensitive to scheduling accuracy. While this results in high throughput and low delay for DC-GBR flows in saturated conditions, the delay performance under DRILL-Q remains comparable, as shown in Fig. 5b, indicating that the channel condition can accommodate prioritizing DC-GBR without compromising the service of GBR flows.

In addition, although DRILL-Q shows balanced resource

distribution across non-GBR flows, we observe that UEs with multiple flows tend to exhibit slightly lower throughput than those with a single flow. This stems from our design principle, where fairness is indirectly incorporated through UE-level measurements, as defined in Eq. (6). Nonetheless, DRILL-Q achieves the most equitable throughput distribution across UEs while satisfying all GFBR requirements.

On the other hand, in the RR and PF schedulers, UE 1 (non-GBR) and UE 4 (GBR), both of which are associated with a single flow, achieve disproportionately high throughput, as observed in Fig. 5a. This result is consistent with the pattern observed in Scenario 2 (Fig. 4), suggesting that these schedulers may inherently tend to favor UEs with single traffic configurations due to the internal logic of the simulator.

D. Jain's Fairness Index

We also evaluate the fairness among flows, as summarized in Table IV. Jain's Fairness Index (JFI) is used to quantify fairness across flow throughputs. In each scenario, we compute the fairness among the QoS resource types (non-GBR,

Fig. 5: Evaluation in Scenario 3 (4 UEs, 6 flows) with 10 MHz bandwidth under OFDMA mode, analyzing the impact of GBR flow inclusion on throughput, delay, and jitter.

GBR, and DC-GBR) that include at least two active flows. Additionally, we assess the overall fairness using a weighted Jain's Fairness Index, where the weight is the inverse of each flow's Priority Level, as formulated in Eq. (14).

$$J = \frac{\left(\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \frac{1}{P_n} \cdot \Lambda_n\right)^2}{\left(\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \frac{1}{P_n}\right) \cdot \left(\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \left(\frac{1}{P_n} \cdot \Lambda_n\right)^2\right)} \quad (14)$$

Here, Λ_n denotes the throughput of flow n , and P_n represents its Priority Level.

In Scenario 1, since there is only one DC-GBR flow, we evaluate fairness only for the non-GBR flows and the overall flow set. The fairness among non-GBR flows is the highest under DRILL-Q (0.97), indicating that it mitigates throughput imbalance between the two non-GBR flows. Interestingly, the total fairness of DRILL-Q (0.85) is slightly lower than that of the QoS scheduler (0.90). This is because DRILL-Q assigns slightly more resources to non-GBR flows than would be allocated purely in proportion to their priorities, due to its use of HOL-based urgency in the scheduling logic.

In Scenario 2, fairness among non-GBR flows drops significantly under the QoS, PF, and RR schedulers, yielding values of 0.52, 0.52, and 0.50, respectively. In contrast, DRILL-Q maintains high fairness at 0.93. As for the DC-GBR flows, fairness is 1.0 across all schedulers. However, in the case of PF and RR, this value results from a degenerate case where both flows receive similarly low throughput, rather than true balanced resource allocation. Consequently, total fairness in PF and RR drops sharply to 0.24 and 0.22, respectively, indicating highly skewed resource distribution.

In Scenario 3, the fairness among non-GBR flows becomes slightly lower compared to Scenario 2, as discussed in Section V-C. Nonetheless, DRILL-Q still achieves the highest fairness (0.88) among schedulers. Similarly to Scenario 2, the fairness among DC-GBR flows remains at 1.0 across all schedulers. However, in the PF and RR schedulers, this again

results from the uniformly low throughput of both flows rather than effective scheduling. On the other hand, our proposed scheduler achieves the highest total fairness at 0.96, as it is the only scheduler that satisfies the GFBR requirements while distributing resources fairly across all flow types.

TABLE IV: Jain's Fairness

Scenario 1 (2 non-GBR and 1 DC-GBR flows)				
Flow Type	DRILL-Q	QoS	PF	RR
non-GBR	0.97	0.84	0.59	0.64
Total	0.85	0.90	0.72	0.73
Scenario 2 (4 non-GBR and 2 DC-GBR flows)				
Flow Type	DRILL-Q	QoS	PF	RR
non-GBR	0.93	0.52	0.52	0.50
DC-GBR	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Total	0.71	0.64	0.24	0.22
Scenario 3 (3 non-GBR, 1 GBR, and 2 DC-GBR flows)				
Flow Type	DRILL-Q	QoS	PF	RR
non-GBR	0.88	0.68	0.38	0.35
DC-GBR	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Total	0.96	0.60	0.41	0.31

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposes a novel RL framework to address user unfairness in QoS provisioning schedulers. In particular, we have presented the DRILL-Q RL-based MAC scheduler, which effectively manages multi-flow traffic while satisfying diverse QoS requirements. By integrating the QoS LC Assignment algorithm for GBR and DC-GBR, DRILL-Q ensures fair resource allocation while guaranteeing the GFBR of these flows. Furthermore, by designing a state representation that reflects the logic of the QoS LC Assignment, we have developed a stable RL model tailored for 5G QoS-aware resource allocation. Our extensive evaluation demonstrates that DRILL-Q mitigates user starvation, improves fairness, and achieves

higher overall throughput compared to traditional scheduling approaches.

Despite these promising results, several challenges remain. As part of future work, we plan to conduct comparisons with other RL-based schedulers to further evaluate the performance of DRILL-Q in dynamic network conditions. Additionally, we aim to extend the model by incorporating channel state information and resource utilization metrics to enhance scheduling efficiency. Another crucial aspect to explore is the computational overhead introduced by the RL-based approach. To address this, we will investigate optimization techniques to accelerate action derivation and convergence, such as prioritized experience replay and parallel and distributed RL, thereby improving real-time applicability. In addition, we aim to extend DRILL-Q to support network slicing, where different slices with distinct QoS requirements coexist. This will involve designing slice-aware reinforcement learning models that dynamically allocate resources across slices while maintaining service-level agreements (SLAs). Lastly, we plan to study the impact of RL-based scheduling on system latency and communication overhead, ensuring that the framework remains scalable for practical deployment in future 5G and beyond networks.

Beyond 5G, future wireless networks are expected to incorporate Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native architectures with advanced network automation and intelligent resource management. In particular, we aim to extend DRILL-Q to support these next-generation networks, where dynamic and adaptive QoS provisioning will be essential. In particular, DRILL-Q can be integrated with Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) to dynamically optimize wireless channels, improving network efficiency under highly dynamic conditions. Additionally, energy-efficient scheduling is another promising direction, where DRILL-Q can be enhanced to minimize power consumption while maintaining QoS guarantees, supporting sustainable 6G networks. These advancements will enable DRILL-Q to adapt to the evolving requirements of next-generation wireless systems, making it a scalable and flexible solution for future AI-driven networks.

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